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RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHY IN CASE OF HERPETIC INFECTION

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ABSTRACT

For scientific research, we conducted tests for herpes infection in patients with chronic dorsopathy, who were treated in the neurology department of the city medical association. It should be noted that chronic dorsopathy was observed in patients with a positive test for herpes simplex virus-2. The diagnosis of herpes simplex virus-2 is made by a combination of anamnestic, epidemiological and clinical data. Anamnesis analysis includes detection of early Herpes simplex virus-2 with differentiation of type 1 and type 2. Laboratory tests are not required to confirm the diagnosis in herpes simplex with characteristic elements of rash and typical morphology. However, in our work, patients with an asymptomatic chronic relapsing course were selected, in which only laboratory tests revealed Herpes simplex virus-2.

Key words: Herpes simplex virus-2, ischioradiculalgia, chronic dorsopathy, osteochondrosis, chronic pain, immunoenzyme analysis.

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РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ КЛИНИКО-НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАНИЙ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ДОРСОПАТИЕЙ ПОЯСНИЧНОГО ОТДЕЛЕНИЯ ПОЗВОНОЧНИКА ПРИ ГЕРПЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ИНФЕКЦИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Для научных исследований мы провели исследование на герпесную инфекцию у больных хронической дорсопатией, находившихся на лечении в неврологическом отделении городского медицинского объединения. Следует отметить, что хроническая дорсопатия наблюдалась у пациентов с положительным тестом на вирус простого герпеса-2. Диагноз вируса простого герпеса-2 ставится на основании совокупности анамнестических,

эпидемиологических и клинических данных. Анализ анамнеза включает обнаружение раннего вируса простого герпеса-2 с дифференцировкой 1-го и 2-го типа. Лабораторные исследования не требуются для подтверждения диагноза при простом герпесе с характерными элементами сыпи и типичной морфологией. Однако в нашу работу были отобраны пациенты с бессимптомным хроническим рецидивирующим течением, у которых только при лабораторных исследованиях был выявлен вирус простого герпеса 2.

Ключевые слова: Вирус простого герпеса-2, ишиорадикулоалгия, хроническая дорсопатия, остеохондроз, хроническая боль, иммуноферментный анализ.

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GERPETIK INFEKSIYA HOLATIDA BEL UMURTQALARI DORSOPATIYA BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA KLINIK VA NEUROLOGIK KO'RSATKICHLARNING NATIJALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ilmiy tadqiqotlar uchun biz surunkali dorsopatiya bilan og'rigan, shaxar tibbiyot birlashmasi nevrologiya bo'limida davolanayotgan bemorlarda herpes infeksiyasi uchun testlar o'tkazdik. Herpes simplex virusi-2 uchun ijobiy tahlili bo'lgan bemorlarda surunkali dorsopatiya kuzatilganiga e'tibor qaratish lozim. Herpes simplex virusi-2 tashxisi anamnestic, epidemiologik va klinik ma'lumotlarning kombinatsiyasi bilan qo'yilgan. Anamnezni tahlil qilish, 1-tur va 2-turni farqlash bilan erta Herpes simplex virusi-2ni aniqlashni o'z ichiga oladi. Toshmalarning xarakterli elementlari va tipik morfologiyasi bo'lgan herpes simplexida tashxisni tasdiqlash uchun laboratoriya tekshiruvlari talab qilinmaydi. Biroq, bizning ishimizda asimptomatik surunkali resitivlanuvchi kursi bo'lgan bemorlar tanlab olindi, unda faqat laboratoriya testlari Herpes simplex virusi-2ni aniqladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Herpes simplex virusi-2, isxioradikuloalgiya, surunkali dorsopatiya, osteoxondroz, surunkali og'riq, immunoferment analiz.

Kirish. Ko'pgina bemorlarda sezuvchanlikning barcha turlarining shikastlanishi kuzatildi: chuqur sezgi buzilishi, og'riq sezuvchanligining pasayishi, vegetativ-trofik kasalliklar. Ushbu guruhning tekshirilgan bemorlarida tos a'zolarining disfunktsiyalari aniqlandi. Neyrovizual sezilarli degenerativ-distrofik o'zgarishlarni aniqladi.

Tadqiqot usullari: Surunkali og'riq sindromi bo'lgan bemorlarni tanlashda, herpes virusi mavjudligi uchun bemorlardan qon olingan. Tahlillar natijalariga ko'ra, biz bu guruhni tashkil etgan herpes simplex bilan og'rigan 35 bemorni o'rganishni o'tkazdik. Jins bo'yicha ayollar – 22 (62,8%), erkaklar – 13 (37,2%). Yosh guruhlarida bemorlarning yosh guruhlari bo'yicha taqsimlanishi quyidagicha edi: 19 yoshgacha - 2 kishi; 19-29 - 6 kishi; 30-39 yosh - 10 kishi; 40-49 - 12 kishi; 50-59 yosh - 5 kishi. Bemorlarning o'rtacha yoshi 36,9 yoshni tashkil etdi (3.4.1-rasm).

1-rasm. Bemorlarning jinsi va yoshi bo'yicha taqsimlanishi

Kasallikning davomiyligi 2 yildan 4 yilgacha davom etdi va o'rtacha 3 yilni tashkil etdi. Bugungi kunga qadar TORCH infeksiyalari zamonaviy tibbiyotning eng o'tkir muammolaridan biri hisoblanadi, chunki qo'zg'atuvchi omillar quyidagilardir: 1) potentsial patogenlar barcha aholi guruhlari orasida keng tarqalgan; 2) klinik belgilarga ega emas yoki asimptomatikdir; 3) immunitet tanqisligi bo'lgan shaxslarning tez kuchayishi; 4) inson salomatligiga asta-sekin salbiy ta'sir.

Tadqiqot natijalari: Surunkali dorsopatiyada og'riqni qo'zg'atuvchi xarakterli belgilar: gipotermiya - 21 (60%); stress - 16 (45,7%); isitma bilan kechadigan yaqinda o'tkazilgan yuqumli kasalliklar - 7 (20%); shuningdek, menopauzadagi ayollar - 5 (14,3%).

Herpes simplex virusining klinik va epidemiologik tashxisini tasdiqlash uchun barcha bemorlarda qon zardobidagi o'ziga xos immunoferment analiz (IFA) yordamida aniqlandi.

2-rasm. Dorsopatiyaning kuchayishini qo'zg'atuvchi asosiy omillar

Olingan ma'lumotlar Dyuden A.D. ning ma'lumotlariga to'g'ri keldi. Bu yerda GGD-1 bo'yin umurtqa pog'onasi dorsopatiyasi bo'lgan 5 bemorning zardobida aniqlangan va 14,3% ni tashkil etgan; qolgan 30 (85,7%) bel umurtqasining dorsopatiyasi bo'lgan bemorlarda GGD-1 aniqlangan. Bemorlarning to'rtinchi guruhida jismoniy tekshiruv vaqtida nafas olish tezligi 1 daqiqada 17 dan 28 martagacha o'zgarib turishi va o'rtacha 22,52, yurak urishi - 67 dan 88 gacha, o'rtacha 1 daqiqada 76,5 urishi aniqlandi. Terining rangpar rangi ustunlik qildi. Limfa tugunlarining kattalashishi aniqlanmagan. Suyak deformatsiyasi va terining namoyon bo'lishi aniqlanmagan.

1-jadval.

Bemorlarda qon zardobidagi maxsus antitela darajasi

Qo'zg'atuvchi omil	Jami bemorlar (N=35)	
	abs.	%
Herpes simplex virusi-1	5	14.3
Herpes simplex virusi-2	30	85,7

Bemorlarning asosiy shikoyatlari umurtqa pog'onasidagi kuchli, yoqimsiz og'riqlar, ko'pincha yonuvchi yoki "elektr toki urishi" shaklida bo'lgan.

3-rasm. Bemorlarda surunkali og'riqni lokalizatsiya qilish

UASH bo'yicha og'riq darajasi 40-88 mm oralig'ida edi. 6 (16,7%) bemor og'riq intensivligini o'rtacha deb ko'rsatdi, qolgan 29 (83,3%) og'riqni yuqori intensivlik deb aytdi. 43 (55,1%) bemorda og'riqni lokalizatsiya qilish sohasida giperesteziya kuzatildi.

2-jadval

Bemorlarda asosiy nevrologik belgilarning paydo bo'lish chastotasi

Belgilari	Barcha bemorlar (N=35)	
	Abs	%
yonuvchi og'rig'i ("elektr toki urishi kabi")	21	60.2
bo'yin mintaqasida og'riq	5	15.4
bel mintaqada og'riq	30	84,6
VASH bo'yicha og'riq darajasi:	o'rtacha	6
	yuqori	29
og'riq sohasidagi giperesteziya	19	55.1
uyqusizlik	13	37,7
shishgan limfa tugunlari	10	29.5
mushaklar kuchining biroz pasayishi	8	24.4
tendon reflekslarini jonlantirish	9	26.9
chuqur sezuvchanlikning pasayishi	24	67,9
og'riq sezuvchanligining pasayishi	19	55.1
vegetativ-trofik buzilishlar	22	64.1
tos a'zolarining disfunktsiyasi	21	61.5
orqa miya rentgenogrammasi	10	28.2

Yuqori intensivlikdagi og'riqlar ko'pincha bemorlarni uyqusizlikka olib keldi - 14 (40 %). Bir qator bemorlarda to'liqroq tekshiruvda limfa tugunlarining kattalashishi aniqladi - 10 (28,5%).

Ushbu guruhdagi bemorlarda xarakat sistemasini o'rganishda quyidagilar aniqlandi: mushaklar kuchining biroz pasayishi - 9 (24,4%), faol va passiv harakatlarda sezilarli o'zgarishlar kuzatilmadi. 9 (26,9%) bemorda tendon reflekslari faollashgan. Ko'pgina bemorlarda sezuvchanlikning barcha turlarining shikastlanishi kuzatildi: chuqur sezgi buzilishi- 24 (67,9%); og'riq sezuvchanligining pasayishi - 19 (55,1%); 22 (64,1%) bemorda vegetativ-trofik buzilishlar

kuzatilgan. Boshqa guruhdagi bemorlardan farqli o'laroq, ushbu guruhdagi tekshirilgan bemorlarda tos a'zolarining disfunktsiyasi aniqlangan - 21 (61,5%).

Bemorlarda neyrovizual tadqiqotlari natijalari

Xulosa: Shunday qilib, bu guruhdagi bemorlarni klinik va nevrologik o'rganish natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, gerpetik etiologiyadagi surunkali og'riq klassik neyropatik xususiyatga ega bo'lib, asosan bel mintaqada kuchli, yoqimsiz his-tuyg'ular, ko'pincha yonuvchi og'riq va "elektr toki urishi" shaklida lokalizatsiya qilinadi, bemorlarning ko'pchiligi oyoqlarga tarqaladigan bel umurtqa pog'onasida yonayotgan og'riqni qayd etdilar. Xarakat sohasini tekshirganda, mushaklarning kuchi biroz pasaygan, faol va passiv harakatlarda sezilarli o'zgarishlar kuzatilmagan.

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9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

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